

A STUDY ON CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND SATISFACTION TOWARDS SELECTED ONLINE SHOPPING IN LEADING COMPANIES

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Abstract:

The basic necessity for a human being is food, cloth and shelter but in modern world ‘internet’ has become a primary need in human life. Online shopping plays an important role in E-commerce. Due to the development progress of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have brought about a lot of changes in shopping, it has been in the form of online shopping or online trading. The main objective of the study is to find out the consumer attitude and satisfaction towards online shopping in Erode District. The study was done based on well structured questionnaire with a sample of 100 respondents. The data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis and chi-square test to find consumer attitude and satisfaction towards selected online shopping in leading companies.

Key Words: Shopping, Online, Attitude, Internet, Satisfaction, Consumers & E-Commerce Etc

Introduction:

The basic necessity for a human being is food, cloth and shelter but in modern world ‘internet’ has become a primary need in human life. Due to the development progress of the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has brought about a lot of changes in shopping, it has been in the form of online shopping. Online shopping is one of the marketing channels through internet which it promotes one to one communication between the seller and the user. Today, online shopping is done all over the world around the clock. Consumers shop through internet because they compare the prices of the product, product features, door delivery facility, consumer service etc., so the consumers feel very comfortable while they are shopping through online. The major difference between traditional and online selling is the communication between the consumer and the seller which done through internet. Consumer’s attitude towards online shopping refers to their psychological state in terms of making purchases over the Internet.

Top Ten Leading Ecommerce Companies:

Amazon: It is one of the leading and reputed online e-commerce platforms acknowledged at a wide scale all over the country. Accessed by millions of people from all over the globe, the marketplace is operated by an affiliate of Amazon.com that is Amazon Seller Services Private Limited.

Flipkart: It is a reputed and one of the esteemed e-commerce platforms used simply all across the world. No matter, whether you are looking for electronics, appliances, anything related to men and women, baby and kids wear, home and furniture, books and more, it is the best platform to seek for.

Snapdeal: is placed at third position in the list of top 10 e-commerce companies in India. Snapdeal was started by alumnus of IIT Delhi in 2010 and within 3 years capture huge share of Indian e-commerce industry. Snapdeal has numerous product categories that include books, mobiles, electronic items, apparels etc. Initially it was started as discount coupon website but to capture growing ecommerce market, Snapdeal has change their business model.

Dealsandyou: is placed at fifth placed. Dealsandyou is a deals website that brings discounted deals of numerous day to day products. Deals help consumers to get discount and also increase the sales of the sellers.

Yebhi.com: is another well-known ecommerce company started in 2009 and within 4 years become the establish player in ecommerce industry. Yebhi was started as BigShoeBazaar.com and then changed its identity to Yebhi. After seen the potential in this company Nexus Venture Partners and N. R. Narayana Murthy’s Catamaran Ventures invested 40 crore in this company.

Caratlane: is a leading jewellery website in India that has product range from Diamond Jewellery, Rings, Earrings, Pendants, Bangles, Necklaces, Nose Pins, Mangalsutra etc.

Shop Clues: is another growing ecommerce company which act as a marketplace between seller and buyer. ShopClues provide delivery in more than 12,000 locations and offers payment options like Net Banking, Credit cards, Debit cards, and Cash Cards. In 2013 ShopClues awarded Best eRetailer of the Year by Indian eRetail Awards 2013

Jabong: is founded in the year 2012 at Gurgaon, Jabong is leading fashion portal of India. They offer more than 90,000 products, 200000+ Styles and over 2000 national and international brands of fashion clothing, shoes, accessories and home-decor. They are very popular among young internet users who are looking for branded clothes and other fashion products at discounted prices. They also have an international store in the name of “Jabongworld.com”.

ebay India: is a 100% subsidiary of international top online e-commerce company - eBay Inc. Started operations in 2014, They are among the biggest managed online e-commerce players in the market with more than 2.1 million active users from 4000+ cities in India. They have more than 1.1 million live product listings on their portal across widest 2,000 categories of products.

Naaptol: is established in the year 2007, Naaptol started as price comparison website. In 2009, they started their online marketplace and pitched their products to consumers online, offline, newspaper advertisements and via TV shopping. Their site has 90,000 visitors visiting them and conducting 5000 transactions a day, which generate daily sales of Rs.1.5 crores.

Need for the Study:

Online Shopping largely depend upon consumer attitudes, preferences and their satisfaction. Due to rapid change in information and communication technology, liberalization, globalization and modernization concept a number of new products and delivery channels have been introduced. With the expansion of large – scale production, growth of competition amongst the producers to capture markets has resulted in the online shopping for almost all kinds of products. Thus, shopping through internet channel plays an important role in present scenario. In this context it is important to study the consumer attitude and satisfaction towards selected online shopping in leading companies.

Review of Literature:

Ashish Bhatt (2014) stated that online shopping is gaining popularity among people specially the younger generation but in today scenario to become equally popular among all age groups e-marketing will have to cover a longer distance. The main objective of this study is to find Consumer Attitude towards Online Shopping in Selected Regions of Gujarat As per study mode of payment is depended upon income of the respondents. People from different age groups are doing online shopping regularly. The paper resulted that attitude of consumers is changing with the time. In a country like India, consumers are finding online shopping very comfortable because of many variables like cash on delivery, customization or personalization of the websites, home delivery etc.

Prashant Singh (2014) revealed that the main objective is to find the consumer’s buying behaviour towards online shopping. The study stated that future of e-retailers in India looking very bright. E-retailers give consumers the best way to save money and time through purchasing online within the range of budget. Flipkart.com offering some of the best prices and completely hassle-free shopping experience. The paper concluded that whole concept of online shopping has altered in terms of consumer’s purchasing or buying behavior and the success of E-tailers in India is depending upon its popularity, its branding image, and its unique policies.

Upasana Kanchan, Naveen Kumar and Abhishek Gupta (2015) evaluated that online purchase behaviour of customers in India. The paper stated that online shopping is gaining popularity among people of young generation. Higher income groups and educated people are purchasing more via e-retailing websites and people have hesitations in doing online shopping due to security concerns. Today people are resistant to change because of technological complexity in making online purchase. The result concluded that companies involved in online retailing should focus on building trustworthy relationship between producers and customers.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the demographic profile of the online shopping consumers in Erode District.
- ✓ To find the consumers attitude towards selected online shopping in leading companies.
- ✓ To identify the consumers satisfaction towards selected online shopping in leading companies.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Erode District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Erode District is the study area. A total of 100 online shopping consumers are taken as sample. These respondents were randomly selected in Erode District. Primary data is collected through well structured questionnaire. The collected information were reviewed and consolidated into a master table. For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test

Analysis and Interpretation:

1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents: Table no.1 describes the demographic profile of the online shopping consumers which is taken for the study. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (58%) of the respondents are male, (49%) whose age group is under 26 to 45 years, most (53%) of the respondents are graduates, maximum number (39%) of respondents are employee, the monthly income of (42%) respondents is up to Rs.10,000, (35%) of the respondents purchase their ticket through online, (50%) of the respondents pay cash on delivery for their online shopping and (36%) of the respondents are motivated to purchase through online shopping because it save their money.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	58	58
Female	42	42
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	26	26
26 to 45	49	49
Above 45	25	25
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	24	24
Graduate	53	53
Professional	23	23
Occupation		
Agriculture	31	31
Employee	39	39
Business	26	26
Others	4	4
Monthly Income		
Up to Rs.10000	42	42
Rs.10000 to Rs.25000	36	36
Above Rs.25000	22	22
Products purchased through online		
Clothes	23	23
Tickets	35	35
Electronic Items	12	12
Cosmetics	14	14
Accessories	16	16
Mode of Payment		
Debit cards/Credit cards	32	32
Online Bank Transfer	28	28
Cash on Delivery	50	50
Motives for buying Online		
Save Time	24	24
Easy to Purchase	26	26
Save Money	36	36
Convenience	14	14

1.2. Relationship between Demographic Variables and Consumers Level of Attitude Towards Online Shopping: Table 2 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables of the consumers and their level of attitude towards online shopping. It is clear that , the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exists any significant association between educational qualification and occupation of the online shopping consumers. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between gender, age and monthly income of the online shopping consumers

Table 2: Relationship between the Demographic Profile and Level of Attitude

Variables	Level of Attitude			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
	Low	Moderate	High				
Gender							
Male	29	20	9	58	13.432	5.991	S
Female	18	18	6	42			

Age (Years)							
Up to 25	10	3	13	26	14.896	9.488	S
26 to 50	23	18	8	49			
Above 50	8	10	7	25			
Occupation							
Agriculture	12	11	8	31	9.845	12.592	NS
Business	7	8	11	26			
Employee	13	15	11	39			
Others	4	7	3	14			
Educational Qualification							
Up to School Level	6	8	10	24	2.178	9.488	NS
Graduate	13	26	14	53			
Professional	5	9	9	23			
Monthly Income							
Up to Rs.10,000	25	6	11	42	15.98	9.488	S
Rs. 10000 to Rs.20,000	13	14	9	36			
Above Rs.20,000	8	6	8	22			

*significant at 5% percent level

1.3. Relationship between Demographic Variables and Consumers Level of Satisfaction Towards Online Shopping: Table 3 depicts the relationship between selected demographic variables of the consumers and their level of satisfaction towards online shopping. It is clear that , the calculated Chi-square value is less than the table value at five percent level, there does not exists any significant association between gender, occupation and educational qualification of the online shopping consumers. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists a significant association between Monthly income and age of the online shopping consumers.

Table 3: Relationship between the Demographic Profile and Level of Satisfaction

Variables	Level of Satisfaction			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
	Low	Moderate	High				
Gender							
Male	19	19	20	58	3.432	5.991	NS
Female	16	10	16	42			
Age (Years)							
Up to 25	7	8	11	26	14.896	9.488	S
26 to 50	18	20	11	49			
Above 50	8	8	9	25			
Occupation							
Agriculture	10	11	10	31	9.845	12.592	NS
Business	11	7	8	26			
Employee	11	13	15	39			
Others	4	5	5	14			
Educational Qualification							
Up to School Level	12	5	7	24	7.178	9.488	NS
Graduate	23	16	14	53			
Professional	7	9	7	23			
Monthly Income							
Up to Rs.10,000	20	16	6	42	15.98	9.488	S
Rs. 10000 to Rs.20,000	11	11	14	36			
Above Rs.20,000	7	7	8	22			

*significant at 5% percent level

Conclusion:

Online shopping is one of the most attractive, widely accepted and highly appreciated business in present world. Behavior of people towards online shopping has changed tremendously. Online shopping will be successful for all type of products or goods only when they have commitment to e-business along with a deeper understanding attitude of consumers needs. The study concludes that consumers play an important for online shopping; once the consumers are satisfied they will bring more consumers.

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